

IMPACT EVALUATION OF REMITTANCE IN NEPAL: A CASE STUDY OF KAILALI DISTRICT

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Abstract: *This is a descriptive cross-sectional study based on the data related to remittance income of respondent households collected from a Municipality and three VDCs of Kailali. The objective of this study are to collect information on the type, volume, and mode of transfer of remittance and, more importantly, to identify foreign employment destination, and its financial cost. Hence, all the households within the study area receiving remittance income for 12 months of the year 2013 were regarded as universe/population of the study. The result of the study shows significant improvement in the living standard of remittance recipient households in terms of education, healthcare expenditure, fuel consumption pattern, source of drinking water, toilet use pattern, access to information, banking habit, insurance policy holding, and women empowerment. Nevertheless, a large proportion (more than 61 percent) of remittance is found to be used in consumption expenditure. It is, therefore, essential to formulate policy measures to divert remittance income to productive sector. Furthermore, 74 percent of HHs have used informal loan to bear the financial cost of foreign employment.*

Keywords: *foreign employment, remittance, gross domestic product, export, import, trade deficit, balance of payment*

Introduction

Remittance has been a significant source of financial inflow to Nepal over the last couple of years. Nepal stands as the third largest economy in the world in terms of the contribution of remittance to nation's Gross Domestic Production (GDP) as it is estimated to be about 25 percent of GDP (World Bank, 2014). Nepal has received remittance amounting to Rs. 434.6 billion in the fiscal year 2069/70 and is projected to receive Rs. 560.6 billion in the fiscal year 2070/71 through institutional channels. In fact it is the result of rapid migration of productive labour force of Nepal to the international labour market. According to the Department of Foreign Employment (DoFE), more than 2.4 million people have been working abroad as migrant workers. But, according to Economic Survey 2014 estimate, more than 3 million Nepalese are working abroad which is a significant chunk for its total population size of 26.6 million (CBS, 2011). According to UNDP Human Development Report 2010, remittance had been one of the factors responsible for the remarkable success in human development of Nepal in the last 40 years. Nepal has emerged as one of the

world's fastest movers in Human Development Index (HDI) since 1970, coming in third among 135 counties studied.

Several researches regarding impact of remittance income have been carried out by national and international scholars. They have assessed the impact of remittance flow in the contemporary world especially the least developed countries. Acharya (2013) stated that the least developed countries at present are seen as the labour exporting countries. He further stated that foreign employment and their remittance has been significantly contributing to socio-economic transformation and, at the same time, it has been posing challenges such as productive utilization, controlling illegal outflow of labour, illegal transfer of remittance, job security and low paying risky jobs.

Prajapati (2013) concludes that for time being, remittance has positive effect but it has far reaching adverse consequences for the nation as a whole and suggests that the nation should retain its workforce.

Bhatta (2012) finds that remittance inflow and the trade deficit are positively correlated and such impact is in an increasing trend. He also points out that remittance inflow helps provide hand-to-mouth provision to the poor as well as improve their living standard. But he also finds a correlation between an upsurge in remittance and the increase in trade deficit. Likewise, Thagunna and Acharya (2012) concluded that the income received from remittance is seen mostly spent on consumption with a very little spending on the productive sector. They also maintained that the economic growth in Nepal, due to higher remittance, is essentially a "pseudo-growth". Pandey and Shrestha (2012) stated that an increasing dependency on remittances has resulted in a number of negative consequences for the Nepalese economy, particularly making it a parasitical economy suffering from the 'Dutch-disease' type effects.

Pant (2011) stated that Nepal's major exports are labour and most of the rural households now rely on at least one member's earning from foreign employment. The upsurge in remittance had led to a surplus in the current account of Balance of Payment (BoP), thereby strengthening the overall BoP position. He recommends that families of migrant workers should be encouraged and trained to run small businesses that will pave way to channelize remittance towards productive use.

A study conducted by Nepal Rastra Bank (2012) reveals that remittance income is mostly spent on unproductive conspicuous consumption, and a significant chunk of remittance is used for land purchase as well. In addition, it also revealed that hundi has still been one of the channels to remit money from abroad.

Irfan (2011) stated that remittance is regarded as a dependable source for growth, improved welfare and poverty alleviation in the developing world. Hoermann *et al.* (2010), in a study carried out in the Western Hinda Kush-Himalayas in Asia, found

out that labour migration and remittance are the major source of livelihood in the study area. Nath and Mamun (2010) mentioned that the remittance transfers received from these migrant workers have reached a phenomenal level of over 10 billion US dollar in 2009, approximately 12 percent of GDP in Bangladesh and has helped reduce poverty in Bangladesh. Orozco (2010) has done a similar study in Bangladesh, which shows that over 70 percent migration takes place to the oil exporting Arab countries

International Centre for International Mountaineering Development (ICIMOD) (2010) conducted a study in the Far Western and Mid Western Development regions of Nepal; the study finds that major portion of remittance is spent in food followed by education, health and consumer goods. Englama (2009) stated that more than 80 percent of remittance is used for daily consumption and concluded that remittance could be a stable and predictable source of external finance for developmental process, when properly used.

Karna (2008) stated that human capital is the wealth of nation and its importance has tremendously increased in recent years, as unskilled, semiskilled and skilled people have shown keen inclination towards foreign employment resulting in the substantial growth of remittance inflow. Shrestha (2008) stated that remittance played a vital role in maintaining macroeconomic stability and keeping the economy afloat and she emphasizes for formulating pro poor migration policy.

The facts mentioned above makes it clear that there is an urgency to formulate appropriate policy options to harness the benefit of increasing remittance inflow. In the 1960s, South Korea had worse economic status than Nepal had, in terms of macroeconomic variables. During this time, South Korea had undergone severe crisis following the war in the Korean peninsula. Due to persistent unemployment problem, Korean youth sought employment abroad, mainly in the Middle East and Turkey. The South Koreans worked there mostly as mining worker and hospital nurses. Most of them even worked overtime. The money sent back home by them eventually contributed to alleviate the foreign exchange reserve constraints. Over the decade, in the 1970s, South Korean economy was booming with around 8.0 percent average annual GDP growth (Thagunna & Acharya, 2012).

Thus, remittance has been an important means of and resource for Nepal to maintain its financial health robust over the last couple of years. With growing number of people leaving for foreign jobs, the remittance has convincingly become one of the main sources of foreign exchange earnings. In fact, the growth of remittance can be an opportunity as well as a challenge. It is worth mentioning that the growth in remittance is the result of labour migration to foreign countries. A sharp rise in labour migration from Nepal has been seen in the recent days. If this trend continues, then Nepal will certainly face the acute shortage of labour in the near future. This critical fact should also be taken into consideration by the government authority and policy makers.

An overview of global remittance flow

Remittance has taken a central place of debates amongst academics, policy makers and development experts. The renewed debate started particularly after 1990s. Theoretically, the developmentalists and neoclassical thinkers during 1950s and 1960s had maintained optimistic views on remittance believing that capital and knowledge transfers of migrants would help achieve development needs of the least developed countries. The same views inform the present debate on the impact of remittance on developing economies (NRB, 2012).

Remittance flows to developing countries have more than quadrupled since 2000. Remittance flows to developing countries are expected to reach US \$ 414 billion in 2013 and US \$ 540 billion by 2016. Worldwide, the remittance flows may reach US \$ 550 billion in 2013 and over US \$ 700 billion by 2016 (World Bank, 2013). The top recipients of officially recorded remittance in 2013 were India (\$ 71 billion), China (\$ 60 billion), Philippines (\$ 26 billion), Mexico (\$ 22 billion), Nigeria (\$ 21 billion), Egypt (\$ 20 billion), Pakistan and Bangladesh each (\$ 15 billion), Vietnam (\$ 11 billion) and Ukraine (\$ 9 billion) (World Bank, 2014).

Figure 1. *Top Ten Remittance Recipient Countries in 2013*

Source: World Bank, 2014

According to World Bank Report, 2014, countries that received a large amount of remittance as a share of the GDP include Tajikistan (48 percent), Kyrgyz Republic (31 percent), Nepal (25 percent), Lesotho (25 percent), Moldova (24 percent), Armenia (21 percent), Haiti (21 percent), Samoa (21 percent), Liberia (20 percent) and Lebanon (17 percent).

Figure 2. Top Ten Remittance Recipient Countries Cased on Remittance/GDP Ratio

Source: World Bank, 2014

Remittance can contribute to reducing poverty and to the building of human and financial capital for the poor, according to the latest issue of World Bank's Migration and Development Brief. Although remittance costs have fallen steadily in recent years, they still remain high in smaller nations where remittance provides a lifeline to the poor. Remittance sent home by migrants to developing countries are three times the size of official development assistance, and it can have profound implications for development and human welfare.

Statement of the problem

Nepal has experienced a sharp rise in remittance inflow over the last couple of years. A higher volume of remittance inflow has raised the standard of living, and has also remained an effective instrument for poverty alleviation, particularly in the rural areas. Most importantly, it has now been the primary component in achieving a favorable balance of payment by narrowing the current account deficit (Thagunna & Acharya, 2012). Remittance for the time being has been contributing to maintain the sound financial health of the economy. But, it has been enhancing consumption expenditure. As a result, import is increasing and trade deficit is widening alarmingly. Nepal is likely to face Dutch Disease types of problems in future days. Dutch disease is the name given to explain the apparent relationship between the increase in exploitation of natural resources and a decline in the manufacturing sector (or agriculture). The term was coined in 1977 to denote the deindustrialization of a nation's economy that occurs when the discovery of a natural resource raises the value of that nation's currency, making manufactured goods less competitive with other

nations, increasing imports and decreasing exports. The term originated in Holland after the discovery of North Sea gas (Dutch Disease, 2014)

Here, it is worth mentioning that every day via Tribhuvan International Airport more than 1500 youth migrate for foreign employment. That is more than 0.54 million in a year. Economic Survey, 2014 mentions that every year about 0.45 million productive youth force enter the Nepalese labour market. The data clearly shows that there is an imbalance between the supply and demand of labour. Obviously, in the near future the country is likely to face acute shortage of labour force. In this connection, the situation has raised some pertinent questions: How to use remittance income in productive sector? Is the remittance inflow coming through formal channel? Can it be a resource curse (Dutch diseases) to the Nepalese economy? Can it be a significant measure to alleviate poverty? Are the people able enough to finance from their own sources, foreign employment? Is the cost of foreign employment affordable to ordinary people? Is it helping to raise wage of the residual labor force living in the community? Is it a permanent means to address the problem of unemployment?

Objectives

The objective of this study is to collect information on the type, volume, and mode of transfer of remittance and, more importantly, to identify foreign employment destinations and its financial cost with specific reference to the area studied. The major objectives are:

- To identify socio-economic impacts of remittance inflow in households that receive remittance money in the selected VDCs of Kailali District.
- To analyze the consumption and utilization pattern of remittance earnings by sample HHs.

Materials and methods

This is a descriptive cross-sectional study conducted in 50 households of Tikapur Municipality, Durgauli VDC, Munuwa VDC and Patharaiya VDC in connection with the primary data of remittance income. The entire study area was divided into four clusters, i.e., Tikapur municipality, Durgauli VDC, Munuwa VDC and Patharaiya VDC. The households (HHs) were chosen randomly as samples from municipalities and VDCs within given limitation clusters (i.e., Tikapur municipality 20 HHs, Durgauli VDC 10 HHs, Munuwa VDC 10 HHs and Patharaiya VDC 10 HHs). Hence, all the households within the study area receiving remittance income for 12 months of the year 2013 are regarded as the universe/population of the study.

This study is based on the primary data as well as relevant secondary data. The primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire that was prepared in the

range of eight sections that contain relevant questions to collect the required information to fulfill the objectives of this study. The purpose and objectives of the study was explained to the respondents. It is assumed that the information and data provided by the respondents are true. The relevant secondary data was collected from the Ministry of Finance Government of Nepal, Central Bureau of statistics, Nepal Rastra Bank, World Bank website etc.

Result and discussion

Household size of respondent HHs

The data shows that the average HHs size of respondent HHs is 6.57 members. This is slightly higher than the Kailali district average of 6.53 members (Kailali District Development Plan, 2068) and national average of Nepal 4.88 members (CBS, 2011) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Average HHs Size

Educational status of children of respondent households

The educational achievement of all children of respondent HHs was found to be good with no cases of drop outs or class repetition. The academic performance of children in terms of their score in the examinations of school was also good.

Source drinking water of households

Source of drinking water is regarded as an important indicator of quality of life. The data reveals that 84 percent of households are using drinking water from tube-well and the remaining 16 percent from piped water supply system (Figure 4).

Figure 4. *Source of Drinking Water*

Types of toilet in respondent households

The data shows that among the respondent HHs, 62 percent have flush toilets, 30 percent have composite toilets and 6 percent pit latrines. 2 percent were found to be practicing open defecation (Figure 5).

Figure 5. *Types of Toilet of Respondent Households*

Fuel consumption pattern of respondent households

The pattern of fuel consumption is another indicator that helps assess the socioeconomic status of the HHs. As per the data collected from sample households, more than half (56%) of the households are found to be using firewood as their major fuel for cooking followed by LPG gas 2%, biogas 14% and electricity 6% (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Fuel Consumption Pattern

Main occupation of respondent household head

Nepal is an agrarian economy and mainstay of people is agriculture. This fact is also reflected in the collected data from sample households. The main occupation of the majority of the respondent households is agriculture (64%) followed by business (24%). Besides, a significant chunk is relying on foreign jobs (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Main Occupation of Respondent Household Head

Educational attainment of emigrant labour

The educational attainment, training and skill play a key role in determining the level of earning for migrant labour in foreign employment. In this connection, data regarding educational attainment of emigrant labour of respondent HHs was collected. The data reveals that mostly twelve class graduates (62%) have gone for foreign jobs. Thereafter, SLC graduates (30 percent) and under SLC (8 percent) have gone to foreign jobs (Figure 8).

Figure 8. *Educational Attainment of Migrant Labour*

Duration of foreign employment

Foreign job duration is another key factor in identifying the attitude and attraction of emigrant labour towards foreign employment. The data reveals that 42 percent are in foreign job for 3 to 5 years, 38 percent for less than 3 years and 20 percent for more than 5 years (Figure 9).

Figure 9. *Duration of Foreign Employment*

Age of respondent migrant labour

The data shows that mostly those aged between 25-40 years have gone for foreign employment. In other words, the data reveals that 78 percent of migrant workers belong to the age group, 25-40 years, followed by less than 25 years (12 percent) and above 40 years (10 percent) (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Age of Respondent Migrant Labour

Financial cost, destination and remittance inflow

Foreign employment destinations are increasingly becoming diversified day by day. But, the data shows that migrant labour prefer Malaysia (MSY) as their foreign employment destination followed by Middle-Eastern nations like United Arab Emirates (UAE), Qatar (QTR), Saudi Arab (SAB) and Kuwait (KWT) (Table 1). Foreign employment (FE) is subject to several types of financial cost (FC). These include consultancy fee, passport and visa processing charge, agency fee, transportation fare and so on. As per the information provided by the respondents, they have incurred NPRs. 2,33,333 in average for South Korea which is the highest and NPRs. 1,48,332 for Malaysia which is the least (Table 1). A great extent of variation occurs in terms of amount remitted from the FE destinations. The data reveals that mean annual from South Korea is NPRs. 10,66,667 which is the highest and NPRs. 3,00,000 from Kuwait, which is the least (Figure 11).

Table 1. FC* for FE**, FE Destination and RMT*** from FE

Category	MSY	SKR	QTR	UAE	KWT	SAB
Percent of migrants	42%	18%	16%	18%	2%	4%
Mean FC for FE (NPRs)	1,48,332	2,33,333	1,71,428	1,50,000	1,50,000	1,50,000
Mean annual RMT income (NPRs.)	4,66,667	10,66,667	6,48,333	5,78,125	3,00,000	4,15,000

*Financial Cost**Foreign Employment***Remittance. Source: Field survey, 2014

Financial source of foreign employment cost

Generally, the migrant labourers belong to lower-middle and lower economic classes. Therefore, in most of the cases, they are not able to manage their own savings

for covering the cost of foreign employment. The data reveals that 74 percent have taken loan from informal/unorganized sources to cover the cost of foreign employment, 14 percent from their own saving and 12 percent from bank loan (Figure 12).

Figure 12. *Financial Source of Foreign Employment Cost*

Land purchase by remittance income

Remittance income is found to be mostly used for land purchase. The data reveals that 56 percent of remittance recipient households have used remittance income for purchase of land (Figure 13). Furthermore, among the land purchasers, 53.60 percent HHs have purchased for the purpose of home construction (COR), 3 HHs have purchased for the purpose of cultivation (CULV) and remaining 10 HHs have purchased with the purpose of reselling for profit (RFPFT) (Figure 14). In other words, land purchase and remittance have a positive relation. This is probably one of the causes for the high demand and inflated price of land.

Figure 13. *Land Purchase*

Figure 14. *Purpose of Land Purchase*

Channel of remittance inflows

Remittance money is received through bank and financial institutions by almost all the HHs. The collected data from the respondent HHs reveals the fact that 98 percent of the remittance recipient HHs receive remittance through bank and financial institutions and only 2 percent through friends (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Channel of Remittance Inflows

Remittance receipt and level of satisfaction on healthcare expenditure

The satisfaction level of respondent HHs on health expenditure is assumed an important measure to assess the adequacy of healthcare status. In fact, it is very difficult to make generalization of the perception in this connection. The respondents were asked about their satisfaction level on healthcare expenditure before and after the remittance income. The collected data reveals that 64 percent of HHs had just adequate healthcare expenditure before remittance income and after remittance income it increased to 84 percent. Likewise, before remittance, 36 percent had less than adequate but it fell to zero after remittance. It implies that remittance income has also improved the healthcare status of respondent households (Table 2).

Table 2. Satisfaction Level on Healthcare Expenditure

Before remittance income			After remittance income		
Less than adequate	Just adequate	More than adequate	Less than adequate	Just adequate	More than adequate
18	32	0	0	42	8
36%	64%	0	0	84%	16%

Source: Field survey, 2014

Access to means of information and communication

Access to means of information and communication determines the living standard of people. It helps a lot to shape idea and raise awareness in people. The data suggest that different means of information and communication are overwhelmingly owned by respondent households. Almost 98 percent of respondent households have owned mobile phones, 94 percent have TVs, 70 percent have DVD players, 30 percent have radios and 30 percent have Public Switched Telephone Network (PSTN).

Ownership of insurance policy, bank account and shares

The data reveals that the respondent households are attracted towards insurance. According to the data, 58 percent of households have insurance policy and almost all have life insurance policy. Bank account holding and share ownership are significant indicators in identifying the financial position of households. All the respondent households have bank account which reflects that there is banking habits among them. At the same time, 34 percent of the households have owned shares (Table 3). This implies that the respondents HHs are in relatively better financial position.

Table 3. *Ownership of Insurance Policy, Bank Account and Shares*

Ownership category	Yes	No	Total
Insurance policy	58%	42%	100%
Bank account	100%	0	100%
Share of financial institutions	34%	66%	100%

Source: Field survey, 2014

Remittance income and its expenditure pattern

The data reveals the fact that a large portion of the remittance income goes towards daily consumption and an insignificant portion goes to capital formation. According to the data, 61.60 percent goes towards daily consumption, 14.13 percent goes towards purchase of household properties, 9.20 percent goes towards education of children, 8.60 percent goes towards repaying loan 5.60 goes towards capital formation and 0.96 percent goes towards other purpose (Table 4).

Table 4. *Expenditure Pattern of Remittance Income*

SN	Particular	Amount (in Rs.)	Percent
1.	Daily consumption	1,79,66,500	61.60
2.	Repaying loan	25,01,000	8.60
3.	Purchase of household properties	41,21,500	14.13
4.	Education of children	26,78,000	9.20
5.	Capital formation	16,24,000	5.60
6.	Others	2,80,000	0.96
	Total	2,91,71,000	100.00

Source: Field survey, 2014

Remittance income and women empowerment

Women empowerment refers to women's capacity to participate as equals among men in all walks of life in the society. The role of women in Nepalese society is different than in developed countries. Some of our social norms and values thwart the efforts of women empowerment. But gradually, Nepal has been making progress in this regard.

The data given in table 6 shows that among the given five indicators of gender empowerment there is better condition for women regarding the participation in decision making after receiving remittance income. As per the information provided by respondents, in most of the cases, the male household head has gone for foreign employment. As a result, their female counterparts are playing the role of the family head; having a dominant role in household decision making processes regarding education of children, health care, financial transactions, community participation and so on (Table 5).

Table 5. *Gender Empowerment*

Gender empowerment indicators	Number of households					
	Before remittance income			After remittance income		
	Male	Female	Both	Male	Female	Both
HHs decision in EDUC ¹	24	0	26	15	5	30
Percent	48.00	0.00	52.00	30.00	10.00	60.00
HHs decision of WHC ²	11	9	30	5	12	33
Percent	22.00	18.00	60.00	10.00	24.00	66.00
HHs decision of FT ³	14	5	31	8	10	32
Percent	28.00	10.00	62.00	16.00	20.00	64.00
HHs decision in FP ⁴	10	5	35	8	6	36
Percent	20.00	10.00	70.00	16.00	12.00	72.00
HHs decision in CPT ⁵	10	9	31	8	10	32
Percent	20.00	18.00	62.00	16.00	20.00	64.00

Source: Field survey, 2014

¹Education of children, ²Women health care, ³Financial transactions, ⁴Family planning &

⁵Community participation

Conclusion

Remittance is the result of labour export to international labour market. Nepal being a developing country is not able to compete in the international commodity market and, as a result, has been exporting labour and making it a source of foreign exchange earning. This trend may have some positive effects in the short run but may create serious problem in the long run. Hence, due attention should be given to gain sustainable benefits from it. In fact, there are positive as well as adverse impacts of remittance in the economy as a whole. The positive impacts are financial benefits,

acquisition of skill, entrepreneurship, exposure, awareness and in some cases empowerment of women, especially those who have become the de facto heads of their households in the absence of men. Based on the findings of this study, positive impacts include: improvement in living standard and healthcare, improvement in children education, banking habits, insurance policy holding, investment in corporate shares, use of modern fuel, improvement in drinking water source, starting of business, poverty reduction, access to information and level of awareness, improvement in toilet use pattern, increasing etc. But, it has adverse impacts as well such as unproductive utilization of remittance, illegal outflow of labour and illegal transfer of remittance, low paying risky jobs, shortage of labor force in national development work, decrease in the use of arable land but rise in land price inflation, family problem etc.

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